

Optical properties of XXL galaxy clusters

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GENERAL CONTEXT

Cosmology with galaxy clusters

- Galaxy cluster (GC): powerful tools for cosmology.
- Major issue: the mass is not a direct observable (mass proxies, scaling relations).
- Other issues: selection functions need to be well understood, systematics and evolutionary effects require precise knowledge of the astrophysical processes in GC.

Fig 1: View of the distribution of the XXL clusters. Some 300 clusters (dots) are shown in the image; the red dots represent the 100 brightest cluster samples. (XXL Collaboration, D. Pomarède). The video is available on-line <http://irfu.cea.fr/xxl>.

The XXL Survey PI: Marguerite Pierre

- The XXL Project is the largest XMM program undertaken since the launch of the telescope.
- The ultimate objective of the XXL project is to constrain cosmology with galaxy clusters between $z=0$ and $z=1$, taking advantage of the intensive multi-wavelength coverage of the fields (from UV to radio). In particular, the goal is the determination of the evolving equation of state of the Dark Energy using galaxy clusters alone.
- It covers two 25 deg² fields, XXL-North and XXL South (see Fig.1), to medium depth and with good uniformity. The completeness limit in the [0.5–2] keV band is $\sim 5 \times 10^{-15}$ erg s⁻¹cm⁻².
- The XXL project is supported by a worldwide consortium of more than a hundred astronomers. Three French institutes are deeply involved in the project: IRFU-Saclay, LAM-Marseille and Lagrange-Nice. The Lagrange node is specialized in the optical-NIR analysis of clusters and in the environmental properties of cluster galaxies.

X-ray and optical-NIR synergy

- Our team is deeply involved in cross-matching X-ray and optical-NIR, especially we are focusing on:
 - X-ray and optical selection functions cross check by comparing the XXL cluster sample to an optical blind search based on the WaZp cluster finder (search for overdensities in photometric redshift space, Benoist et al. 2017 in preparation) (see Fig.2).
 - Exploration of various definition of optical mass proxies such as richnesses and luminosities and comparison to the X-ray proxies. Investigation of the galaxy population in clusters over a wide redshift range to control associated systematics and scatters.

Fig 2 : A 3deg² tile illustrating the WaZp cluster finder. Example of a cluster with highest significance in the $z=0.35$ galaxy density slice.

LUMINOSITY FUNCTIONS OF THE XXL CLUSTER GALAXIES

Ricci et al. In prep.

Motivations

- Investigate the luminous distribution in X-ray selected clusters.
- Study how does light traces mass.
- Learn about formation and evolution of galaxies in dense environments.

Objectives and method

- Study the optical luminosity functions (LF) of a uniform sample of 173 low mass GC from XXL-N, with spectroscopic confirmation and spanning a wide range in redshift (see Fig.3).
- Check for redshift evolution and mass dependence.

Fig 3. Top: Location of the clusters in the plan of the sky, each black circle represents a 1Mpc radius centered on the X-ray position, the gray map is the combined visibility map from CFHT-W1 and XXL-N, bottom: redshift distribution of the cluster sample.

Fig 4. Example of a galaxy cluster which is part of a superstructure Left: composite g'r'i' image of the cluster+1Mpc field, the X-ray contours are shown in green, red circles are early-type galaxies and the yellow circle indicates the BCG. Right: Density map of the cluster 10 * 10Mpc field. The white contours indicate the structures detected by WaZp, the red circle shows R = 1Mpc around the cluster X-ray center and the dashed lines delimitate the field used as local background.

- Optical data: photometry in the u*g'r'i'z' bands of Megacam @ CFHT with associated photo-zs.
- Cluster members selection using redshift slices with redshift and magnitude dependant widths. Contribution of background galaxies removed by subtracting counts in local fields (see Fig.4).
- Homogeneous richness estimation up to $z=1$. Individual LF computed in absolute and apparent magnitudes. Composite cluster LF computed to enhance the SNR.

Results

- Individual LFs up to $z=1.22$ (see Fig.5):
 - Large fraction of poor groups/clusters.
 - Diversity of LF shapes.
 - Fiducial LF parameters for >60% of the sample.
- Composite cluster LF as a function a mass and redshift (see Fig.6).
 - LF of poor clusters really different from the others.
 - Evolution of the amplitude of the LF with richness (~cluster mass), even if rescaled by R500.
 - No evidence of evolution of the faint end slope with redshift.
 - Evolution with redshift following passive evolution.

Fig 5. Left: g'r'i' composite images of the 0.5Mpc fields around X-ray centers, X-ray emission contours are in green, the BCG is circled in yellow. Middle: density maps of selected XXL clusters with increasing redshifts from top to bottom, the legend is a same as in Fig 4. Right : luminosity functions of the same clusters, in absolute magnitude in the r' band, except for the one at $z=1.22$ which is in apparent magnitude in the i' band. Schechter functions are fitted in red.

Fig 6: Composite clusters LFs 68% confidence intervals for different bin of richness (left) and redshift (right). The different lines indicates the ranges constrained by the data for each bin. The CLFs have been computed in scaled radius of R500, and rescaled by R500 in order to take into account the 3rd dimension.

Perspectives

- Investigate LF radial dependence
- Investigate effect of the cluster morphology and dynamical state
- Re-do the analysis using luminosity in the K-band that is a better tracer of the total mass.
- Separate the galaxy population by colors.

Conclusion

- We studied the optical luminosity functions of 173 XXL-North galaxy groups/clusters. The sample spans a wide redshift range ($0.03 < z < 1.22$) in the poorly studied low mass regime. It allows to check for evolutionary effects and mass and morphology dependences, in a homogeneous way.
- We developed a precise method for the cluster galaxies membership assignment, using at the best the photometric redshift. For each cluster we computed richness and luminosity function in apparent and absolute magnitudes. We then construct composite cluster LF and investigate evolution with redshift and richness.

Our first results indicates that our richness estimation is well correlated to the X-ray luminosity (and thus to the cluster mass). The sample is composed of a large fraction of optically poor groups/clusters, that may not be detected by optical searches. Using composite clusters LF in different richness and redshift bins, we find that the amplitude of the LF increases with richness, even is rescaled to R500. The faint end slope do not seems to evolves with redshift, but the LF are shifted to lower luminosity with cosmic time, following passive evolution. The LF of the poorest groups/clusters is very different from the other, with much more faint galaxies compare to the bright ones.

This is an ongoing work (Ricci et al. 2017 in prep).

Acknowledgments

XXL is an international project based around an XMM Very Large Programme surveying two 25 deg² extragalactic fields at a depth of $\sim 5 \times 10^{-15}$ erg cm⁻² s⁻¹ in the [0.5–2] keV band for point-like sources. The XXL website is <http://irfu.cea.fr/xxl>. Multi-band information and spectroscopic follow-up of the X-ray sources are obtained through a number of survey programmes, summarised at <http://xxlmultiwave.pbworks.com/>.

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